

A New Approach to Astatistical Stabilisation of Cu(II) Ternary Complexes Containing Tertiary Amines and O—O⁻ Co-ordinating Ligands

P. K. BHATTACHARYA* and P. J. PATEL

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

The formation constants of the complexes of the type [CuAL], where A=2,2'-dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole or 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline and L=acetylacetonate or benzylacetone have been determined in dioxan-water (1 : 1 v/v) solutions and $\mu=0.2$ (NaClO₄) at 30°. The formation constant values have been determined by graphical method and further refined by using a computer programme. The value of $\Delta \log K$ ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M$) is found to be positive in [CuAL] complexes. The fact that $\Delta \log K$ is positive in Cu(II) complexes, can be explained to be due to repulsion between metal d π electrons and electron density over L. The study of uv and visible spectra also confirm this concept.

THE name organic is synonymous with life and hence the term "bio inorganic" appears self contradictory. But it has been recently realised that the metal ions have an important role to play in biochemical reactions. Inorganic chemists have thus been encouraged to synthesise model compounds which closely mimic the naturally occurring compounds. Through the study of the properties of these synthetic models, they try to evolve principles governing the biochemical processes.

Study of the mixed-ligand complexes¹⁻³ is gaining importance because it provides models for the metalloenzyme reactions. The mixed-ligand complexes, involving aromatic tertiary amines, are being studied in detail because of the similarity of the aromatic tertiary amines with imidazole which occurs commonly in metalloenzymes.

Ternary complex formation is statistically favoured. There is further astatistical^{3,5} stabilisation due to various reasons. In the complexes [MAL], where A is a tertiary diamine like dipyridyl, it has been observed that the mixed-ligand formation constant K_{MAL}^{MA} is higher than expected from statistical considerations⁴. This has been explained to be due to M→dipy π interaction^{5,6}. As a result, the electron density over the metal ion is reduced and the effective electronegativity of [MA]²⁺ is almost the same as [M(H₂O)₆]²⁺. Thus, the σ bonding tendency of L to combine with [CuA]²⁺ is not significantly reduced. As M→A π interaction goes on increasing the ternary complex is stabilised more⁷.

[MA] complexes are known to have discriminating effect towards secondary ligand (L) with co-ordinating atoms, N-N, N-O⁻ and O⁻-O⁻. The stabilisation of ternary complexes [MAL] is in the order O⁻-O⁻ > O⁻-N > N-N. In [CuAL] complexes the stabilisation is greater and $\Delta \log K$ ($\log K_{CuAL}^{CuA} - \log K_{CuL}^{CuL}$) is positive, in cases where L

co-ordinates through two O⁻. This extra stabilisation was explained by Sigel⁹ to be due to inter-ligand π interaction between A and L through the metal d π orbital where L is catechol. However, a positive $\Delta \log K$ is observed even when L is purely σ bonding ligand like malonate ion^{10,11}. In order to explain such cases an alternate explanation was extended by us in terms of electron repulsion¹¹⁻¹³. In the formation of binary complexes, there is electron repulsion between the metal d π electrons and the lone pair of electrons (if any) present on the σ bonding ligand L. However, in ternary complexes, due to back donation of electron through π bonding from the metal ion to A molecule, the electron density on [CuA]²⁺ is reduced. Therefore, the repulsion between the metal d π electrons and the additional lone pair of electrons over the secondary ligand (L) is less in the ternary complexes. There is no extra lone pair of electrons present on σ bonding N atom and hence this effect is not felt in N-N co-ordinating ligands. In ligand co-ordinating through N-O⁻ there is lone pair of electrons over the carboxylate O⁻. Due to the decrease of the electron repulsion in the ternary complexes, $\Delta \log K$ is much less negative in N-O⁻ than in N-N co-ordinating ligands. In case of malonate, there are lone pair of electrons over both carboxylate anions and hence the effect is more pronounced leading to positive $\Delta \log K$ in [CuAL].

Even in cases of complexes [CuAL], where L=anions of catechol, dihydroxynaphthalene or its derivatives¹⁴, salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-naphthaldehyde or its derivative¹⁵, it has been shown by uv spectral studies that though there is π interaction in [CuA₂] and [CuL₂] complexes, there is one to one correspondence between the uv spectral bands of the mixed-ligand complex [CuAL] with that of [CuA] and [CuL], with no significant change in band positions. This shows that there is no interligand π interaction between A and L through the metal d π orbitals, as suggested by

Sigel⁹. Hence, in these complexes also the greater stabilisation and positive $\Delta \log K$ can be explained¹¹⁻¹⁵ in terms of the lowering of the repulsion between metal $d\pi$ electrons and the ligand lone pair electrons in the ternary complex.

In the case of [CuAL], where L is 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene, $\Delta \log K$ is less positive than in the case of catechol, because the electron density due to the extra lone pair of electrons over two O⁻ is delocalised over two rings. Thus, the repulsion effect is less in the binary complex and lowering of repulsion is also less in the ternary complex leading to a less positive $\Delta \log K$ value. In the case of 1,8-dihydroxynaphthalene with the two O⁻ on the two different benzene rings, the stabilization of the ternary complex is still less and $\Delta \log K$ is negative, though the coordination of L is from two O⁻.

It had been observed by Sigel¹⁶ earlier that electron-withdrawing substituents over L lower the stability of the ternary complex, whereas electron-donating groups increase the stability. He could not, however, extend any explanation in terms of the concept of interligand π interaction. It was observed by us in [Cu-A-tiron], [Cu-A-protocatechate] and [Cu-A-pyrogallol] complexes¹⁴ that $\Delta \log K$ values are less positive than in the case of [Cu-A-catecholate]. This can be explained in terms of our concept of lowering of electron repulsion in the ternary complex. The substituted sulphonate, carboxylate or the hydroxy group withdraws electron density from the ring. Thus, the negative charge over O⁻ is less in these cases than in the unsubstituted catecholate and hence $\Delta \log K$ is less positive.

In ternary complexes, [CuAL], where L = dopamine or adrenaline also $\Delta \log K$ is less positive or negative. This is because the amino group does not take part in coordination. This remains protonated in the range of coordination of the ligand. This protonated amino group withdraws electrons from the catecholate ring and hence the ternary complexes are not stabilised to the same extent as in the case of [Cu-A-catecholate].

The study of [Cu-A-catecholate], type of complexes is interesting because they provide a model for metalloenzyme reactions. The effect of substituted group, not directly coordinating to the metal ion, on the ternary complex stability also throws light on the role of the substituents on the carrier ligand, not directly involved in coordination with metal ion, on the stability of the metalloenzyme substrate complex.

β -Diketone complexes are known to have pseudo aromatic character due to π interaction between the metal $d\pi$ electrons and $p\pi$ electrons delocalised over the diketone ion¹⁷. In [Cu(dipy)(acac)], $\Delta \log K$ was found to be nearly zero indicating greater stabilization of the ternary complex¹⁸. However, in case of the ternary complexes [CuAL], where L = β -ketoanilide, $\Delta \log K$ is positive¹⁹. Thus, though Cu $\rightarrow$ β -ketoanilide π interaction is less, the

ternary complexes involving β -ketoanilide are more stable. This has been explained to be due to the presence of an additional lone pair of electron over the anilide nitrogen which increases the electron density in the β -ketoanilide chelate ring leading to positive $\Delta \log K$. Similar effect and positive $\Delta \log K$ is observed in ternary complexes of the type [CuAL], where L = salicylanilide derivatives¹⁸. By the substitution of an electron withdrawing bromine group over the secondary ligand, $\Delta \log K$ is found to be less positive.

In the present work, study of the complexes [CuAL], where A = 2,2'-dipyridyl (A¹), 1,10-phenanthroline (A²), 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole (A³) or 2-(2'-pyridyl)-imidazoline (A⁴) and L = acetylacetone (L¹) or benzylacetone (L²) have been carried out. The structures of ligands A are shown in Fig. 1.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade except 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole and 2-(2'-pyridyl)imidazoline which were prepared by known method²⁰. TLC and melting points indicate purity of the compounds. Analysis agrees with expected percentage of C, H and N.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants were determined in dioxan-water (1 : 1 v/v) solution and $\mu = 0.2$ (NaClO₄) at 30°.

The values of $n\bar{H}$, K_1^H , $\bar{n}$, pL , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by carrying out normal Irving-Rossotti titration^{20,21}. The titrations were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen in thermostatic bath with temperature $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The formation constants of ternary complexes were determined by an extension of Irving-Rossotti technique⁶. Expanded scale pH meter, pH 821 of Elico make, with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH units was used. At $\bar{n} = 0.5$ in the formation curve, $pL = \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. More precise values were obtained by plotting pL against $\log 1 - \bar{n}/\bar{n}$ and obtaining a straight line, wherein $\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = pL - \log 1 - \bar{n}/\bar{n}$. The average values have been recorded in Table 2. In each individual measurement, pH values were corrected for dioxan-water (1 : 1 v/v) medium using the method suggested by Van Uitert and Hass²².

All the formation constants were subjected to refinement by using the computer programme

SCOGS²⁸. The refined values of proton-ligand and binary metal-ligand formation constants were first obtained. These refined values were used for the refinement of the ternary complex formation constants in two ways :

- (i) by considering the species present in the solution to be LH, L, [CuA] and [CuAL]
- and (ii) taking into account all possible species to be present in solution i.e., LH, L, AH₂, A, [CuL], [CuL₂], [CuA], [CuA₂] and [CuAL].

The refined values obtained by the computer technique, have been presented in Tables 1 and 2. In cases of [CuA³L] and [CuA⁴L], calculation of

spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells using dioxan-water (1 : 1 v/v) as solvents. Solutions of concentration 10⁻⁴ to 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ were used for uv and visible regions, respectively. Spectra of free ligand, [CuA₂], [CuL₂] and [CuAL], prepared by direct mixing of Cu(II) and ligands in required proportions, were obtained.

Results and Discussion

It is interesting to observe that in the case of the ternary complex [CuAL]⁺, the values of the formation constants obtained by the use of the extension of Irving-Rossotti titration technique, presuming the formation of complex in two distinct separate steps, Cu + A ⇌ [CuA] and [CuA] + L ⇌ [CuAL], and the values obtained by using the computer technique are nearly equal in all the cases. This shows that the presumption, that [CuA]²⁺ formation is almost complete in the lower pH range and L⁻ combines with [CuA]²⁺ in forming [CuAL]⁺, is valid. This is further confirmed by observing the

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND BINARY COMPLEX STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Cu(II) IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 1 v/v) AND μ=0.2 (NaClO₄) AT 30°

Ligand	K ₁ ^H	log K _{CuL} ^{Cu}	log K _{CuL₂} ^{Cu}
L ⁺	9.48	9.45	7.91
L ²⁺	9.56	9.88	7.84

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cu(II) IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 1 v/v) AND μ=0.2 (NaClO₄) AT 30°

		log K _{CuAL} ^{Cu}			log K _{CuAL} ^{Cu}			log K _{CuAL} ^{Cu}		
		A ²	Alog K	I	A ³	Alog K	I	A ⁴	Alog K	I
L ⁺	9.70	9.56	+0.11	9.70	9.56	+0.11	10.00	10.12	+0.56	9.00
L ²⁺	9.90	10.31	+0.38	9.88	9.98	+0.15	10.60	10.68	+0.80	9.40
										9.18
										9.50
										-0.32
										-0.88

I—An extension of Irving-Rossotti titration technique.
II—Computer method.

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND ENERGIES (nm) AND log ε OF FREE LIGANDS, BINARY COMPLEXES AND MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES IN DIOXAN-WATER (1 : 1 v/v) MEDIUM

Compound	nm (log ε)
A ⁺	236.9(4.18), 289.1(4.18)
[CuA ²] ²⁺	240.9(4.6), 301.2(4.56), 312.5(4.51), 714.3(2.79)
L ⁺	279.3(4.08)
L ²⁺	250(3.87), 316.4(3.50)
[CuL ²] ₂	289.1(3.98), 384.6(2.44), 666.6
[CuL ²] ₂	251.2(3.76), 322.5(3.90), 387.5(3.41), 322.5
[CuA ² L] ²⁺	243.9(4.04), 289.0(4.07), 295.8(4.14), 312.5(3.95), 387.5(2.53), 625(1.89)
[CuA ³ L] ⁺	251.2(4.22), 301.2(4.26), 312.5(4.24), 335.5(3.90), 384.6(3.47), 621.1(1.75)

mixed-ligand formation constants considering all possible species could not be done. This is because formation of [CuA³] and [CuA⁴] is complete at very low pH and hence the formation constant of [CuA³] and [CuA⁴] could not be determined by pH metric titration. The formation constants were, therefore, determined by presuming complete formation of [CuA].

Spectral measurement: The spectra were recorded on a Carl Zeiss Specord UV visible

plot of the concentration of various species (as percentage of total Cu²⁺ present) against pH as shown in Fig. 2. It is observed that in the lower pH range Cu²⁺ and [CuA]²⁺ are major species and in the higher pH range the major species are [CuA]²⁺ and [CuAL]⁺ totalling to almost 100%. The concentration of other species are negligible.

It is observed that Δlog K is positive except when A = A⁴. The value of mixed-ligand formation

constants depends on Cu→A π interaction and the order is found to be as follows :

It shows that Cu→A π interaction in $[\text{CuA}^1]$ and $[\text{CuA}^2]$ are of equal extent. However, in $[\text{CuA}^3]$ the co-ordination is from one pyridine N and one benzimidazole ring N and hence Cu→A π interaction is greater. This results in an increase in the formation constants of ternary complexes and $\Delta \log K$ becomes more positive. In the cases of $[\text{CuA}^4\text{L}]$, $\Delta \log K$ is found to be negative because there is co-ordination from one pyridine N and one imidazole ring N. π interaction is possible only with pyridine ring as imidazole ring is saturated and has no delocalized π electron cloud. Thus, it is less π interacting than the other primary ligands A^1 , A^2 and A^3 .

In order to explain the positive $\Delta \log K$ value in $[\text{CuAL}]$ complexes, Sigel and coworkers⁹ considered interligand π interaction between A and L. A similar explanation could be extended for the present $[\text{CuAL}]$ complexes. However, an observation of the uv spectra of the complexes does not support interligand π interaction.

UV spectra : The specific bands are discussed in the ternary complexes, $[\text{CuA}^1\text{L}_1]^+$. Dipyridyl (A^1) shows bands at 236.9 and 289.1 nm. The band in the lower energy region corresponds to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. On co-ordination with metal ion $[\text{CuA}_2]^2+$ shows bands at 243.9, 301.2 and 312.5 nm. The appearance of a new band and shift in $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition shows that there is interaction between π orbitals of Cu(II) and those of dipyridyl molecule. The band in acetylacetone (L^1) is observed at 279.3 nm. In the case of $[\text{CuL}_2]$, bands are observed at 288.1 nm and 384.6 nm. The band at 384.6 nm corresponds to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. This indicates that there is ligand to metal charge transfer interaction.

In the ternary complex $[\text{CuA}^1\text{L}_1]^+$ there is almost one to one correspondance of bands with that in $[\text{CuA}_2]^2+$ and $[\text{CuL}_2]$, with no significant change in their positions. Thus, although there is metal-ligand π interaction in the binary complexes, there is no significant change in the π orbital energies due to mixed-ligand complex formation. This indicates that in these complexes also there is no significant interligand π interaction through metal dπ orbitals. The spectra of other $[\text{CuAL}]$ complexes revealed the same fact.

An alternative explanation has, therefore, to be extended for positive $\Delta \log K$ values in these complexes. The greater stability of the ternary complexes can be explained in terms of release of electron-repulsion. In the formation of the binary complex, there is electron-repulsion between the metal ion dπ electrons and lone pairs of electrons present over the O^- of ligand L. This repulsion lowers down the formation constant of $[\text{CuL}]$ complexes. However, in the ternary complexes, there is

back donation of metal dπ electrons to the primary ligand through π bonding and hence the electron density on the metal ion is reduced in $[\text{CuA}]^{2+}$, resulting in lowering of repulsion between metal dπ electrons and the ligand lone pair of electrons. Hence, the tendency of L to combine with $[\text{CuA}]^{2+}$ is more than the tendency to combine with Cu^{2+} , and $\log K_{\text{CuAL}}^{\text{CuA}}$ is greater than $\log K_{\text{CuL}}^{\text{Cu}}$ resulting in positive $\Delta \log K$ in ternary complexes [A-Cu-acetylacetone] and [A-Cu-benzylacetone].

Visible spectra : The study of ligand field spectrum is also interesting. It is normally expected that in mixed-ligand complex [MAL], the ligand field splitting is average of that in the two binary complexes $[\text{MA}_2]$ and $[\text{ML}_2]$. However, in the complexes of the present study $[\text{CuA}^1\text{L}_1]^+$, where L co-ordinate through $\text{O}-\text{O}^-$, the d-d transition band is at higher energy than in $[\text{CuL}_2]$ or $[\text{CuA}_2]^2+$. This is because Cu→dipy π interaction stabilises L→Cu σ interaction (where L co-ordinates through $\text{O}-\text{O}^-$) due to lowering in electron-repulsion between metal dπ electrons and the lone pair of electrons over O^- . Conversely, L→M σ interaction increases M→dipy π interaction. Thus, the two ligands mutually stabilise each other. Consequently, ligands A and L create stronger field in $[\text{CuAL}]$ than in $[\text{CuA}_2]$ or $[\text{CuL}_2]$. The positive shift in the d-d band position of $[\text{CuAL}]^+$ complex from the average of $[\text{CuA}_2]$ and $[\text{CuL}_2]$ can be considered as the extent of stabilisation of the ternary complex.

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